

Original Article

Survey on Leadership, Commitment with Organization and Intentions Behind Turnover in Private Schools, Quetta

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Abstract

Employees are the pivotal part of any organization. They are nurtured through training and experience. Every organization wants to retain their productive employees. On the other hand, employees look for better opportunities. Baluchistan has been suffering from many social issues and education is one of many issues. Private schools thrive to provide quality education in the province.

The study relates on the situation of turnover intention in private schools in Quetta City. Different private schools in surrounding area and main Quetta city were included in the study. A survey through structured questionnaire was performed after acquiring the consent from all the participants and informing them of the academic purpose of study. Internal consistency of all the items have been checked and found satisfactory. After descriptive statistics, correlation among variables is reported and values are within acceptable range. Using Ordinary least square method, leadership styles are used as predictors while commitment with organization being mediator. Research found leadership style can significantly decrease turnover intention while organizational commitment remains important mediator.

The study proposes leadership styles are the cornerstone for improving employees' performance, hence these need to be considered in working out better plans for employees' performance. Organizations need to work on improving organizational commitment of employees by owning them and providing them with a conducive work environment

Keywords: productive employees, turnover intention, organizational commitment, mediating role.

Introduction

For a successful organization, management holds a prominent position for the smooth running of that organization. In the system of education, the school principal is playing this leadership role which is multifaceted and integral for the success of the organization. A good principal effectively manages operational management and instructional leadership tasks for the success of the school. Further an effective school principal plays a significant role that fosters a positive school culture, as well as promotes the engagement of the community in the educational processes. Primarily, a school principal sets the educational standards and best achievable goals, fosters better collaboration and cooperation of teaching and non-teaching staff as well as ensures the best teaching and learning environment in school for their students. Principal plays a crucial role and fulfills the basic responsibility by providing a conducive and supportive environment for both teachers and students. When a school principal plays their best role for their teachers this will lead towards the satisfied

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and motivated teachers which further referred to as the committed workforce. Ultimately, these teachers play an important role and aim to nurture intellectual, social, and emotional development of their students.

Recently, the concept of organizational commitment has also gained considerable attention as every organization is seeking for the committed workforce to enhance overall performance and productivity, reduce turnover, and foster a positive workplace culture. Organizational commitment indicates the loyalty and emotional connection of an employee by supporting the goals, values, and overall mission of their organization. Employees' commitment certainly reflects higher job satisfaction, motivation, and retention. Given the dynamic nature of today's competitive business environment, organizations are increasingly recognizing that the commitment of their workforce to their organization is directly linked to the overall performance of their organization.

Primarily, teachers play an important role for the better future of students and society as whole. Teachers are imparting knowledge to their students and guiding them in their personal, emotional, and social development. Undoubtedly teachers are the central to the educational system as well as to the whole development of individuals and societies. Undeniably, teachers are influencing the academic development as well as social and emotional growth of the students. Further teachers are impacting on students' inspiration and motivation, also serving them cultural and moral guidance. Most commonly teachers help their students by becoming their role models and help them build lifelong skills. Their influence is not limited within the boundaries of the classroom but extends far beyond it, deeply impacting on personal and professional lives of their students.

In many systems of education, the issues of teachers' turnover is a significant concern as it can have negative impacts on student achievement, school culture, and the stability of educational institutions. Though teachers have key positions in the whole system of education, their turnover intention can have more diverse impact on the broader development of their students and society. Generally, a teacher's turnover intention can refer to the intent of teachers for leaving their current position or their teaching profession altogether. Most commonly different factors such as; Organizational commitment, Job satisfaction related with the work environment and workload, Compensation and benefits, Lack of professional development, Student behavior and classroom management, Administrative support, Work life balance, whereas, some other factors such as broader societal factors including family needs, personal health, or economic conditions contribute to teacher turnover intention and these can influence on teacher's decision to leave their teaching profession. Teachers may leave their position to get more stability, flexibility, or financial security. Administration support critically fosters teachers' organizational commitment and detracts the turnover intention.

Although much has been written about the significance of leadership and organizational commitment for organizational performance and productivity, fewer studies have focused on the understanding about the importance of leadership style and organizational commitment for teacher turnover intentions for organization's better performance and productivity. This research aims to discuss leadership, organizational commitment and turnover intention in Private school, in Quetta. This study considers the various aspects of leadership and organizational commitment for ensuring maximum retention of committed workforce. This study focuses on a close examination of leadership, organizational commitment and turnover intention which can impart knowledge for workforce retention. Moreover, it offers actionable insights to those institutions that are striving to solve the problem of workforce retention by implementing employee-focused strategies for the improvement of their overall organizational performance.

Statement of the Problem

Balochistan has been facing many social problems. Poor quality of education tops the list of social problems. Private schools, like in other parts of Pakistan, have been trying to fill the gap in terms of provision of education and maintaining quality. But due to frequent turnover of teachers, most schools have not succeeded in their efforts. This research is an attempt to know the impact of leadership style on turnover intention of private school teachers in Quetta city.

Research Objective

1. To analyze the impact of leadership on teacher's turnover intention in private schools of Quetta.
2. To analyze the impact of organizational commitment on teachers' turnover intention in private schools of Quetta.
3. To check if organizational commitment has mediating role.

Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant impact of leadership on teacher's turnover intention in private schools of Quetta.

H₀₂: There is no significant impact of organizational commitment on teacher's turnover intention in private schools of Quetta.

H₀₃: Organizational commitment does not mediate leadership styles.

Scope of the Study

This study covered the private schools registered in the city Quetta and approved by the Government of Pakistan.

The study is specifically determined to examine the impact of leadership and organizational commitment on teacher turnover intention in private schools of Quetta.

Review of Related Literature

The researchers have delved the issue rigorously as it is very important to find out more and more factors affecting turnover intention. This study goes through the relevant literature one by one

Turnover Intention

The turnover intention is referred to as an employees' intent of leaving the present position or organization. And employees' turnover intention may have some association with different components, i.e. Leadership Style, Organizational commitment, Job satisfaction, Workplace environment, Opportunities for career development, and Employees' personal or professional challenges.

The issue of employees' turnover intention is crucial in every field because the retention of talented workforce is directly related to the success of the organization. Employees' having higher turnover intention may want to switch their prevalent position to seek employment elsewhere, while those with low turnover intention shows a higher commitment and stays longer in their organizations. A kind of situation where employees with high turnover intentions may lead to their unsatisfactory performance, which is further a great loss of that organization. Hence, to reduce employee attrition and improve retention strategies, crucially there is need to understand its importance, to minimize and overcome the intention of being turned over by employees.

A research study conducted by Cohen et al. (2015) argued that regarding researches intended to study on employees' turnover, most of them are consistently focused on the employees' turnover intention instead of studying about their tangible turnover. And these researches assumed that this intention of leaving intention somehow indicates towards a proxy for and predicts the intention of employees for their actual turnover. The findings of this study suggested for future researches to study turnover intention and actual turnover in organizations as two different concepts which can be studied by focusing on different sets of variables. And further this study concluded that those leaders who worked on employees' retention need to focus on the prominent demographic aspects and relevant administration policies of their respective agency instead of studying the employees' self-reported cumulative rates on turnover intention.

Additionally, study conducted by Belete (2018) explained that the concept of turnover intention is inexplicit in nature; and also burdensome in the identification of reasons that forced employees to leave their current position. Conceptually this research intended to identify factors that are influencing on employees' turnover intention from review of various empirical works considering the relationship focused only on few factors that can be commonly identified in any organization, such as, organizational commitment, salary,

leadership styles, job satisfaction, job stress, etc, and also pointing out the other considerable factors, such as, perceived organizational support, supervisor support, job autonomy, opportunities for training and development, and benefits for employees.

Leadership and Turnover Intention

Leadership demands qualities such as emotional intelligence, resilience, adaptability, and communication skills. It encompasses various responsibilities and functions to guide, inspire, and influence individuals or teams toward achieving common organizational goals. Generally, it is leader's responsibility to set clear & achievable goals, to strategic decision-making regarding resources, operations, or personnel and for motivating individuals or teams to work collaboratively.

Effective leadership goes beyond just directing others; and can be practiced in various contexts, from business to community efforts. Depending upon the context, an effective leader defines the direction and vision for the organization, inspires and encourages team members during challenges or changes, ensures clear, transparent and effective communication, provides guidance, feedback and opportunities for growth, supports the development of their team members, and fosters a positive culture by setting an example for others, and by demonstrating the values, ethics, and behaviors expected in the organization.

Regarding this, Gan and Voon (2021) in their research study aiming to establish a relationship between employee job satisfaction and transformational leadership style, by considering their impact for the reducing employees' turnover intention. This study confirmed that the decision regarding staying or leaving the organization made by an employee has higher influence of job satisfaction and transformational leadership style.

Further, Wakabi (2013) stated that leaders play an important role in retention of employees, as their leadership styles have great influence on the perceptions of employees regarding the organization. This research is intended to find impacts of a leader's leadership style for the retention of employees in organizations and this study claims that employees' turnover intention is greatly influenced by leadership styles, moreover, highlights the significance for the selection of best leadership style for the promotion of employees' retention.

Other researchers such as Ntenga and Awuor (2018) argued that at organizational level poor leadership is the most common reason for employees' higher turnovers, further the organizations that promote leadership development can get deep-rooted advantages. Regarding the analysis on the leadership style and employee turnover intention, this research claimed that increase in transformational leadership style, transactional leadership, laissez-faire leadership style and democratic leadership style leads towards the increase in employees' turnover intention. Hence, this study suggested that leaders recognize their own errors and correct them, as they had comprehensive knowledge about the useful social control mechanisms.

Another research conducted by Alzubi (2018) states that the opening of doors for new talents and ideas can minimize turnovers rate, and higher turnover rates are distracting and impact negatively on organizational status. This research endeavors to analyze the influence of leadership style, organizational commitment and organizational culture on employees' turnover intentions at higher levels of education, particularly in Jordan. And this research found that leadership behaviour, organizational commitment and organizational culture significantly impacted turnover intentions. Therefore, leaders must improve their leadership behavior that can increase employees' level of commitment and reduce employees' turnover intentions.

Organizational Commitment and Turnover Intention

The organizational commitment refers to the employees' psychological attachment and loyalty that they feel for their organization. Further, it reflects the degree to which an employee is committed to identify set goals, values, and mission of the organization, and are motivated to contribute to its success. High organizational commitment often leads to increased job satisfaction, improved performance, and reduced turnover rates.

There are typically three components of organizational commitment: Affective Commitment; referred to the employee's feeling of emotional attachment towards their organization, Continuance Commitment

referred as employee's feelings of obligation and rational decision to remain with organization because of the know-how about the leaving costs, and Normative Commitment; referred to the employee's feelings of obligation or their sense of loyalty or reciprocity to stay with organization due to some moral and ethical reasons. With strong organizational commitment employees most prominently play significant roles and remain dedicated to the missions and long-term objectives of organization.

The study of Gyensare et al. (2017) aimed to determine the mediating role of employee engagement and affective commitment in relationship between transformational leadership and employees' voluntary turnover intention. Further it investigates the moderating role of psychological climate in relationship between affective organisational commitment and employees' voluntary turnover intention. And findings of this study revealed a positive influence of transformational leadership on employees' engagement, that further indicates a negative relationship with employee turnover intention. Moreover, employee engagement plays a mediating role between transformational leadership and affective organisational commitment. While employee engagement and affective organisational commitment play a mediating role between transformational leadership and voluntary turnover intention. Lastly, psychological climate plays a moderating role between affective commitment and voluntary turnover intention.

Another study of Guzeller & Celiker (2019) expected to reveal the association between organizational commitment and turnover intention in the literature of hospitality and tourism. In this study those researches intended to study the association between organizational commitment and turnover intention in (tourism and hospitality) industry was systematically identified by a comprehensive literature review. Findings of this study showed that organizational commitment and turnover intention have a negatively moderating relationship. Regarding findings, the employees having higher emotional commitments with their organizations show lower turnover intentions compared to others. For the reinforcement of organizational commitment, recruitment of talented employees and promoting employees' retention, some of the important aspects need to be considered by an organization, such as, the selection of right personals, performance evaluation techniques, promotions, training & career opportunities and talent management and functional virtues indicating strong communication, trust, and justice, etc.

Another research of Mosadeghrad et al. (2008) intended to demonstrate the association of job satisfaction and employees' organizational commitment by noticing their influence on employees' turnover intention, specifically at Isfahan Hospitals, Isfahan Iran. This study revealed employees' moderate level of satisfaction and commitment with their job and organization. Expectedly, employees' job satisfaction is positively correlated with organizational commitment but unexpectedly these were also positively correlated with turnover intention. This might be because some of the variables, like conditions related to the job market, have a great impact on perceived opportunities for career advancement elsewhere. Since employees' job satisfaction, organizational commitment and employees' turnover show higher association, therefore, application of appropriate human resource policies can help regarding their best reinforcement.

The research conducted by Yucel (2012) aimed to study the association between employees' job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and turnover intentions. And results indicate that employees' job satisfaction as a preceding variable for employees' organizational commitment and turnover intentions. Hence, employees' job satisfaction positively influences employees' commitment (i.e. affective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment) and indicates negative impacts on employees' turnover intentions.

Data and Methodology

The present study is quantitative in nature. Its philosophy is positivism since it measures a quantifiable concept. This study emanating from theory hence its research approach is deductive in nature. The research strategy is survey through a structured questionnaire, and its time horizon is cross-sectional.

Research design

This is a study that uses quantitative and cross-sectional research design. This research investigates the relationship between transformational, transactional styles of leadership and organizational commitment (as predictors) and turnover intention (as response variable). The study area of this research is private schools in Quetta. This research is based on established theories hence it is deductive in nature. The study employs Ordinary Least Square for checking hypothesis.

Research methods

The present study is about exploring the effect of transactional leadership and employee organizational commitment on turnover intention. The target population of the study is private school teachers, admin staff and head of schools.

Instrument used in this study

This study uses a 5 points Likert scale questionnaire. Where one shows strongly disagree while 2 disagree, 3 shows neutral response while 4 and 5 are used for agree and strongly agree respectively. Transformational leadership is measured through 15 items, transactional leadership by 5, 15 items are used to measure organizational commitment, and 11 items are used to measure turnover intention. Reverse order questions are used for all four variables in order to tackle the response bias. These constructs are adopted from different studies, and its internal consistency is crucial to be determined beforehand, Cronbach (1951). Transformational leadership scales were taken from the study of Podsakof et al (1990) and its higher value, e.g. more than 0.7, indicates that all the items measure the construct well. Its items were reduced to 15 from 17 after the piloting round. Its Cronbach's alpha value is 0.73. Transactional leadership is also taken from the study of Podsakof et al (1990) and Cronbach's alpha value is 0.71. its one item was reduced in piloting stage due to confusion faced by respondents. Items for Turnover intention are taken from the study of Kelloway, Gottlieb, and Barham's (1999) and its Cronbach's alpha is 0.78. items for measuring organizational commitment was adopted from the study of Mowday et al., (1979). Its Cronbech's alpha is 0.79.

The population of this study is all private schools in Quetta city. All the surrounding area schools of Quetta city including Sattelite town, Saryab, Pashtoon abad, Alamdar road, hazara town, main city, Nawa kili, and Pashto abad were visited. This study acquired formal consent from all the participants and informed them of the academic purpose of study. The research uses non-probability sampling, and Convenient sampling for both school selection and respondents. This method is considered cost effective, and it is more practical in nature (Etikan, Musa, & Alkassim, 2016). Few schools denied access while others didn't agree to accept questionnaires. Therefore, those schools and respondents were selected which not allowed me to school but also agreed to filling the questionnaires. Due to lack of digital literacy, I had to provide questionnaire in hard form. Furthermore, I personally visited the school where I also explained the questionnaire as it had some technical terms like transactional and transformational leadership for better understanding of the respondents. In total I provided 400 questionnaires and collected 320, which makes a response rate of 80%. There were 23 incomplete responses, so I had 297 responses for analysis.

Explanation of variables

In total four variables are used in the study. These variables are explained as below:

Commitment with organization: in education, commitment with organization means the psychological attachment and emotional bond that educators (teachers, staff, administrators) feel towards their school or educational institution. It reflects their identification with and dedication to the school's mission, values, and goals, leading to increased effort, engagement, and a desire to stay with the organization.

Transactional leader: In educational settings, transactional leadership focuses on exchange of rewards and punishments to motivate and guide students or educators. This approach emphasizes clear expectations, performance standards, and a system of incentives for achieving goals or consequences for falling short. It's often characterized by a directive style where the leader sets the agenda and monitors progress, ensuring tasks are completed and outcomes are met.

Transformational leadership: Transformational leadership in education is a leadership style that inspires and motivates followers, including teachers, students, and staff, to achieve a shared vision and improve the overall educational experience. It emphasizes building a positive and supportive environment, fostering innovation, and promoting continuous growth and development.

Turnover intention: In reference to a school education, turnover intention refers to a teacher's plan or desire to leave their current school or teaching position. It signifies the likelihood of a teacher voluntarily quitting or seeking employment elsewhere.

It is important for any data to be analyzed for different aspects before it is used for econometric analysis. Descriptive statistics provide a detailed picture of mean and variation. The following table describes data for variation, range and central tendency.

Table:1 Description of Data

Variables	Mean	Variations	Max	Min
Turnover Intention	3.9	0.78	5	1
Organizational Commitment	3.1	1.32	5	1
Transformational Leadership	2.8	1.61	5	1
Transactional Leadership	3.5	1.1	5	1

The current data set measures items on 5-point Likert scale. Its variation and average values are important indicators for data understanding as it shows mean and variation Hair et al. (2014).

In survey analysis and questionnaire, it is imperative to find if items measure the construct with consistency. When a construct is measured with multiple items it becomes essential to know if these items are measuring the construct effectively. The following tables explain the internal consistency of items with the help of Cronbach's alpha values.

Table:2 Consistency of items

Construct	Number of Questions used (items)	Cronbach's alpha values
Turnover Intention	11	0.81
Organizational Commitment	15	0.75
Transformational Leadership	15	0.87
Transactional Leadership	5	0.79

The integrity of items and the way it measures the construct is important. Its value needs to be greater or equal to 0.7 in order to convincingly say about its efficacy in measuring variable (George & Mallery, 2019). In above table all the values are in the range of effective measurement and internal consistency is established.

Table:3 Correlation among variables

Variable	TOI	OC	TR	TF
TOI	1	-	-	-
OC	0.57	1	-	-
TR	0.70	0.58	1	-
TF	0.63	0.61	1	1

Correlation value is an important indicator of association of variables, and its value lies between 0 and 1, where 0 shows no correlation while 1 represents complete association. These values show the strength and direction of the variables. (Dancey & Riedy, 2017) have defined its acceptable ranges, correlation values 0.1 to 0.3, 0.4 to 0.6 and 0.6 and above are considered weak, moderate and strong correlation respectively. The values in above table show both moderate and strong association.

Econometric strategy, result discussion

This research uses Ordinary Least Square. OLS can be very useful in establishing mediation and indirect effects Hayes, 2013 and Preacher and Hayes 2004). Following Baron and Kenny (1986), four different models are used to find commitment with organization mediation while the indirect and direct role of leadership styles on turnover intention. Following four models are used:

$$TOI = \beta_1 + \beta_2trl + \beta_3tl + \epsilon \quad (1)$$

$$oc = \beta_4 + \beta_5trl + \beta_6tl + \eta \quad (2)$$

$$TOI = \beta_7 + \beta_8oc + \theta \quad (3)$$

$$TOI = \beta_9 + \beta_{10}trl + \beta_{11}tl + \beta_{11}oc + \Omega \quad (4)$$

Where TOI, oc, trl and tl represent turnover intention, organizational commitment, transformational leadership and transactional leadership respectively. While β_s are constant terms and coefficients of said variables. ϵ , η , θ and Ω are error or catch all terms.

Regression results of all four OLS models

Table:1

Predictor	Model 1 (TOI)	Model 2 (OC)	Model 3 (TOI)	Model 4 (TOI)
Transformational Leadership (Trl)	-0.301**	0.373**		-0.201**
Transactional Leadership (Tl)	-0.262**	0.297*		-0.181**
Organizational Commitment (OC)			-0.478*	-0.270*
Constant	0.162	2.300**	0.259	0.784**
R-squared	0.548	0.367	0.487	0.647
N	297	297	297	297

Note. **p < .01; *p < .05

The current study uses Ordinary Least Square to confirm the effects of leadership styles and organizational commitment on turnover intention in private schools in Quetta city. Four models have been used separately in order to establish the mediating role of organizational commitment. Model one has both leadership styles as predictors while turnover intention being predicted. In Model Two, organizational commitment is predicted by organizational styles as predictors. Organizational commitment appears as predictor in third model while turnover intention is predicted. Fourth model has leadership styles and organizational commitment as predictors while variation in turnover intention is explained. In first model both styles of leadership reduce turnover intention. In 2nd model, organizational commitment is significantly affected by leadership styles. Third model explains variation in turnover intention by organizational commitment; this shows when organizational commitment improves it decreases the chance for an employee to change its organization. Fourth model is the ultimate interest of this study, if organizational commitment remains significant and even its significance improves in presence of leadership styles, this affirms the mediating role organizational commitment. The result in 4th model confirms this and hence the impact of organizational styles and mediating role played by organizational commitment on turnover intention is confirmed.

Path diagram of the structural model

A priori \ shows direct effect --> indicates indirect effect and \searrow signifies mediating effect.

This diagram explains the path of the effect of both transactional and transformational leadership style mediated through organizational commitment. Initially both leadership styles affect organizational commitment positively and in the second model organizational commitment also decreases turnover intention of the employee. Furthermore, leadership styles decrease turnover intention of the employee in the third model. In forth model all three predictors, leadership styles and organizational commitment decreases turnover intention of the employee, in this model the presence of organizational commitment reduces the effect of leadership styles which confirms the mediating role of organizational commitment in the model.

Result and discussion

Turnover of teachers has been a serious problem for private schools as they have not been able to retain teachers who spend time at respective schools. The turnover of teachers affects school performance, and this also gives a negative reflection of the school. In this research we attempted to determine how leadership styles can reduce turnover intention and how organizational commitment mediates in this process. Following Baron and Kenny (1986), In model one both leadership styles have been the predictors, and their effect is not only significant but also reducing turnover intention. The second model organizational commitment is dependent variable and leadership styles are used as predictors. Both styles significantly improve organizational commitment. In third model organizational commitment reduces turnover intention. Here we get a clue that organizational commitment may be playing the role of a moderator in this system. For this reason, forth model is run. Where leadership styles and organizational commitment are predictors. In this model the effect of leadership style was reduced compared to model one (but still it is significant) due to the presence of organizational commitment. This confirms the mediating role of organizational commitment. All these results are shown in table 1. Showing both p values and β s.

Policy implication

Employees are real assets of any organization, and it is paramount for any organization to be able to retain their employees. Leadership is integral part of improving service delivery in any set up. It becomes more important in schooling process as subordinates look into organization through leadership. This is leader who brings employees closer to organization and improves attachment. These in turn can be vital in retaining employees in organization. The current study links leadership style and organizational commitment and then connects them directly and indirectly with turnover intention. For any organization to improve its performance through reducing turnover intention, it is pertinent to focus on leadership style which improves organizational commitment and reduces turnover intention

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